

MULTIPARAMETRIC ULTRASONIC DIAGNOSTICS OF SOFT TISSUE TUMORS

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Abstract. *It is important to suggest that the problem of early diagnostics of tumors of the musculoskeletal system is still far from being solved. Traditional examination methods, including a complex of various modifications of X-ray examinations, are associated with high radiation loads, are expensive and are limited in their repeated use in terms of both diagnostics or evaluation of treatment results, and subsequent dynamic observation for the purpose of early detection of relapse of the disease. At the same time, already in the first reports on ultrasound examination (US) of soft tissues, it was noted that tomograms reveal details that are not determined by radiography.*

Further studies have shown that the echography method allows to determine the nature of the pathological process with high differential diagnostic accuracy, and the capabilities of ultrasound in detecting soft tissue tumors (STT) are not only not inferior, but in some cases even surpass the sensitivity of the X-ray method, including CT [1,3,4]. Doppler techniques open up completely new prospects in ultrasound diagnostics of volumetric soft tissue formations [5,6].

Definitely, the desire to systematize information on the capabilities of complex ultrasound tomography in the diagnosis of soft tissue neoplasms, as well as to determine the informativeness of the method in assessing the effectiveness of treatment and early diagnosis of relapses served as the reason for this publication.

Keywords: *soft tissue, echographic studies, x-ray, malignant neoplasms, ultrasound semiotics, musculoskeletal system.*

Purpose of the study. To improve the diagnosis of soft tissue tumors through the use of complex echographic studies.

Materials and methods of research. In order to clarify the ultrasound semiotics, we analyzed the ultrasound results of 174 patients with soft tissue diseases observed from 2019 to 2023. Malignant neoplasms were detected in 126 (72%) patients, benign tumors in 41 (24%), and non-neoplastic changes in 7 (4%). Modern ultrasound tomographs allow obtaining a detailed image of the tissues and structures of the musculoskeletal system. The use of multi-frequency sensors with the ability to change the operating scanning frequencies in the range from 5 to 13.5 MHz makes it possible to determine the presence of pathological changes in soft tissues - mainly when examining large areas of soft tissue (hip, gluteal region) and in patients with excess body weight, convex sensors with low scanning frequencies (2-5 MHz) were used.

It is known to everyone the size of the resulting ultrasound image is limited by the width of the sensor used. Therefore, with extensive changes, determining the true boundaries of the tumor process, the relationship of the tumor with the surrounding areas makes up to 60 cm in length. The algorithm of the diagnostic search for ultrasound of the musculoskeletal system can be formulated quite briefly: sequential study and analysis of the image from the skin level to the underlying bone structures in order to identify or exclude a volumetric formation. While visualizing a volumetric formation, its localization is determined, the shape, size (in three mutually perpendicular planes)

and the number of nodes, its contours, internal structure and the intensity of reflection of ultrasound waves from it, the presence and thickness of the capsule are assessed.

Certainly, the condition of the tissues surrounding the neoplasm (edema, infiltration, thickening and/or damage to the integrity of the surface of bone structures) is necessarily recorded and, finally, the degree of tumor vascularization and the condition of the main vessels (displacement, deformation, infiltration, presence of blood clots) are studied.

For identifying and assessing the condition of the main vessels and the degree of vascularization of neoplasms, the power Doppler mode was used. This technique is a modification of the color mapping mode and differs from the original in that it allows displaying a two-dimensional picture of the location and shape of the vessels, highlighting them in one color against the background of a conventional B-mode image. In this sense, it is close to the method of X-ray contrast angiography and allows observing vessels with low blood flow velocities and small diameters. The advantages of the technique are almost complete independence from the Doppler scanning angle and increased sensitivity compared to other Doppler techniques, a high frame rate and the absence of ambiguity in spectrum measurement. In order to determine the capabilities of Dopplerographic methods in the diagnosis of malignant neoplasms of soft tissues and to identify the characteristics of the nature of blood flow, color and energy mapping methods, as well as pulse-wave Dopplerography, were used. The results of Dopplerography of 110 patients were analyzed. In 16 (13%) patients, blood flow in the tumor was not visualized.

Depending on the number of intratumor vessels, all observations were conditionally divided into the following groups: Type I blood flow - with the presence of a single vessel; Type II blood flow - with the presence of 2 to 5 vessels, Type III blood flow - with visualization of more than 5 vessels.

Results and discussion. While comparing the histological type of tumor and its size, it was found that synovial sarcoma often had small sizes (from 0 to 3 cm and from 3.1 to 6.0 cm). The largest number of patients with node sizes from 3.1 to 6.0 cm and more than 15.1 cm were tracked in the group with liposarcoma. Patients with malignant fibrous histiocytoma (MFH) were found in all the selected groups, but most often with tumor sizes from 6.1 to 9 cm and from 12.1 to 15 cm. A similar trend can be found in the analysis of other, rarer forms of soft tissue sarcomas.

Given the data provided, it is impossible to distinguish any histological variant of the neoplasm by its size. However, malignant tumors larger than 9 cm are significantly more common ($p < 0.001$). Most malignant tumors were represented by a single node - 51.0% of patients. Multinodular structure of the neoplasm (3 or more nodes) was found in 35.0% of patients. Solid structure was more typical for such neoplasms as synovial sarcoma and rare sarcomas ($p < 0.001$). ZFG and liposarcomas represented the largest group in both single-node and multinodular tumor development variants.

Thus, malignant neoplasms of soft tissues significantly more often have an irregular shape - 61% ($p < 0.05$), uneven contour - 78% ($p < 0.01$), heterogeneous structure - 84% ($p < 0.01$) and are usually represented by a solid formation - 95% ($p < 0.01$), with reduced intensity of reflection from the tumor - 75% ($p < 0.05$). The sign of clarity and blurriness of the contours of malignant neoplasms did not have significant differences, since they occurred in almost the same number of cases - 56 and 44%, respectively. Solid-cystic or cystic structure is not characteristic of malignant tumors of soft tissues and was determined only in 3% of patients with MFG and myogenic sarcoma. Areas of increased intensity were observed in 17% of cases and, during morphological

examination, corresponded to the proliferation of connective tissue. Calcifications were represented by inclusions with acoustic shadow and were visualized in 14% of observations. In most cases, when assessing the characteristics of the ultrasound picture of various histological variants of malignant neoplasms of soft tissues, pathognomonic ultrasound signs were not revealed. Only for liposarcomas in 60% of observations was an increased intensity of reflections from the structure of the formation characteristic.

It should be suggested that ultrasound tomography can also be used to assess the tumor spread to surrounding tissues, bones, and its relation to major vessels. In our study, ultrasound examination revealed soft tissue tumor spread to bone in 3 cases, which was confirmed by morphological examination of postoperative material. When distributing patients based on the nature of vascularization, it was noted that a single tumor vessel was detected in 7.3% of cases. Most neoplasms were characterized by images of 2 to 5 vessels — 63.6%, and visualization of more than 5 vessels in a node was observed in 29.1% of patients; Type II blood flow was observed in all histological forms of tumors in the vast majority of cases — up to 100% in the group with neurogenic sarcomas; Blood flow type III was detected in fewer cases, and its prevalence in the group with lymphosarcoma is explained by the significant size of tumor nodes - from 9.1 to 12 cm. Blood flow types II and III were significantly more common in patients with malignant tumors of soft tissues ($p < 0.001$). While conducting pulsed-wave Dopplerography, blood flow velocity indices and peripheral resistance indices were calculated and assessed. A pronounced spread of absolute hemodynamic indices was noted for all histological types of tumors. Therefore, it is not possible to identify the dependence of a certain histological variant on hemodynamic indices.

Moreover, all malignant neoplasms were characterized by high values of peripheral resistance indices, which, apparently, can be explained by the peculiarity of the structure of tumor vessels, which are tortuous structures with multiple areas of stenosis and occlusion. Perhaps this explains the large spread of absolute values of blood flow indices in intratumor vessels, which does not contradict the literature data. It should be noted that the highest values of velocity indices were recorded in patients with neurogenic and angiogenic sarcomas - up to 68 and 60 cm / s, respectively. When studying the ultrasound semiotics of benign neoplasms of soft tissues in B-mode, the results of a study of 41 patients were analyzed. It was revealed that benign neoplasms are more likely to have a relatively small size - up to 3 cm (34.3%), which was observed in neurofibroma, myxoma and giant cell tumors ($p < 0.001$). Only desmoid and lipoma reached large sizes – 15 cm and more. The majority of patients with benign tumors were characterized by the presence of one tumor node – 85.4%. The exception were patients with lipoma, where in one case 2 nodes were observed, and the multinodular form with the presence of three or more nodes was encountered only with desmoids.

While analyzing the data obtained, we noted a pattern of ultrasound signs characteristic of most benign tumors (excluding desmoids).

However, diagnostics of soft tissue tumors causes certain difficulties and therefore requires special consideration with an analysis of errors and difficulties in the diagnostic process. Quite often, patients diagnosed with a soft tissue tumor actually have a non-neoplastic disease. At the same time, there are quite a lot of pathological processes similar to soft tissue neoplasms. For this purpose, we initially determined the capabilities of ultrasound tomography in visualizing soft tissue neoplasms with subsequent differential diagnostics of tumor and non-neoplastic changes.

Moreover, the group of non-neoplastic diseases included patients with an inflammatory process (ossifying myositis, hygroma, villonodular tenosynovitis) and organized hematoma. The inflammatory process is characterized by the absence of a tumor node, soft tissue edema and increased vascularization on ultrasound tomograms. Ossifying myositis was a chronic inflammatory area of irregular shape, heterogeneous structure with areas of increased intensity and isolated vessels. Hygroma was defined as a cystic formation with heterogeneous contents, septa and isolated vessels in the capsule.

It is not a secret that villonodular tenosynovitis is classified as a "non-neoplastic or doubtfully neoplastic process resembling true neoplasms" (WHO). The process often affects large joints and is characterized by a pronounced thickening of the synovial membrane of the joint with nodular and villous growths during morphological examination. On ultrasound tomograms, it is visualized as a solid formation of irregular shape with an uneven contour and heterogeneous structure, located in the area of the joint with a single vessel along the periphery. On ultrasound tomograms, the organized hematoma was a rounded formation with a clear, even contour, heterogeneous cellular structure and the absence of blood flow in it. Its echogenicity depended on the duration of existence and the appearance of fibrous and calcified inclusions in it. Of the patients examined for soft tissue diseases, the volumetric formation and its tumor and non-tumor affiliation were correctly identified in 98% of cases. True positive cases were recorded in 96%, and true negative cases were recorded in 2% of cases, when a correct conclusion was made about non-tumor changes. Patients with non-tumor changes in soft tissues (ossifying myositis, hygroma and villonodular tenosynovitis) were given erroneous conclusions (2%), which are included in the group with false positive results. Analyzing the errors in the results of ultrasound examination, they should be explained by a combination of atypical ultrasound signs - the presence of a nodular formation of irregular shape, heterogeneous structure and visualization of vessels in it, which is typical of the tumor process. False negative conclusions were not expressed in any case.

Thus, the sensitivity of ultrasound tomography in diagnosing soft tissue neoplasms was 100%, specificity was 57%, and accuracy was 98%. Using the described complexes of ultrasound signs, 85% of patients with benign and malignant neoplasms gave the correct conclusion. False positive cases were identified in patients with a newly established diagnosis of soft tissue desmoid due to the similarity of the ultrasound picture inherent in malignant neoplasms. False negative data were obtained in observations when small formations of a regular round or oval shape, with a smooth contour and homogeneous structure, with no blood flow were determined. The presented picture was interpreted as benign, but morphological verification revealed the malignant nature of these tumors. The indicators of diagnostic information content of ultrasound tomography in diagnosing malignant tumors of soft tissues were: sensitivity - 92%, specificity - 65%, accuracy - 85%.

Conclusions. It should be suggested that the complex ultrasound examination is a highly informative diagnostic method in patients with soft tissue formations in the neck, trunk and limbs. It allows not only to identify the tumor node, assess its size, localization, relationship with surrounding structures, but also, using Dopplerography and elastography, to say with a high degree of probability about the benign or malignant nature of growth, and in some cases to approach the morphological characteristics of the neoplasm. Reduced echogenicity of the tumor, false capsule, heterogeneity of the echostructure, uneven tuberos borders, intense blood supply, high stiffness

coefficient in elastography, deep location, in our opinion, can be regarded as signs pathognomonic specifically for malignant extraorgan neoplasms of soft tissues.

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